

```

# R code for Marzban et al (I).
# Disclaimer: This code is not written by a professional coder.

library(terra)           # For reading data.
library(MatchIt)        # For matchit().
library(marginaleffects) # For avg_comparisons()
library(fields)         # For image.plot()

my.transf = function(M)  # Function for orienting an image in image(),
{
temp <- M
  for(i in 1:nrow(M))
    temp[i,] <- M[nrow(M)-i+1,]
return(t(temp))
}

my.rasterize = function(M) # Function for converting 3d to 2d array.
{
tt <- dim(M)
nr <- tt[1]
nc <- tt[2]
nt <- tt[3]
N <- matrix(nrow=nr*nc, ncol = nt)
  for(k in 1:nt)
    N[,k] <- c(M[, ,k])
return(N)
}

nn <- 8000      # Number of sampled grid points, about half of dat.
ntrial <- 4     # Number of trials/samples of size nn.
discard <- "none" # Discard points outside common-support of PS (Stuart
2010).

treatn <- 401   # Downward shortwave radiation flux
outcomen <- 268 # Surface potential temperature
confn <- c(     # Geopotential height at 29 pressure levels:
  17, 25, 33, 41, 49, # 17=100hPa 25=125hPa 33=150hPa 41=175hPa 49=200hPa
  57, 65, 73, 81, 89, # 57=225hPa 65=250hPa 73=275hPa 81=300hPa 89=350hPa
  97, 105, 113, 121, 129, # 97=400hPa 105=450hPa 113=500hPa 121=550hPa
129=600hPa
  138, 147, 156, 165, 174, # 138=650hPa 147=700hPa 156=725hPa 165=750hPa
174=775hPa
  183, 192, 201, 211, 220, # 183=800hPa 192=825hPa 201=850hPa 211=875hPa
220=900hPa
  229, 238, 247, 256) # 229=925hPa 238=950hPa 247=975hPa 256=1000hPa
nconf <- length(confn)

Col <- colorRampPalette(c("darkblue", "blue", "darkgreen", "green", "white",
"orange", "darkorange", "red", "darkred"))(100)
place <- c(.15, .90, .97, 0.99) # Location of color bar.

##### read in data and crop #####

grib_data <- terra::rast("narrmon-a_221_20010101_0000_000.grb")
colNames <- paste(names(grib_data), as.character(time(grib_data)), sep="_")
Dat <- array(dim = dim(grib_data))
for(i in 1:418)
Dat[, ,i] <- matrix(grib_data[, ,i], nrow=dim(grib_data)[1], byrow=T)

```

```

exrow_left <- 120 # exclude longitudes/west
exrow_right <- 80 # exclude longitudes/east
excol <- 80 # exclude latitudes
x0 <- 1 + excol ; xf <- 277 - excol # rows of Dat
y0 <- 1 + exrow_left ; yf <- 349 - exrow_right # cols of Dat
dat_crop <- Dat[x0:xf, y0:yf,]
image(my.transf(dat_crop[, , outcomen]), col=Col)

dat <- my.rasterize(dat_crop)
rm(grib_data, Dat, dat_crop)

##### looking at correlations #####

Corr_treat <- Corr_outcome <- matrix(nrow=nconf, ncol=2)
for(i in 1:nconf){
Corr_treat[i,] <- cor.test(dat[,treatn], dat[,confn[i]])$conf
Corr_outcome[i,] <- cor.test(dat[,outcomen], dat[,confn[i]])$conf
}
x11()
boxplot(t(Corr_treat), ylim=c(0.7,1), axes=F, xlab="Confounder/Height (gpm)",
ylab="Correlation", col=0)
boxplot(t(Corr_outcome), add=T, axes=F, border=2, col=0)
axis(1, labels=paste0("X",1:nconf), at=c(1:nconf), cex.axis=1); axis(2, labels=T);
box()

conf <- dat[,confn]
x11()
Corr = cor(conf)^4
image(Corr, col=Col, axes=F)
axis(1, labels=c(1:29), at=seq(0,1,length=29))
axis(2, labels=c(1:29), at=seq(0,1,length=29))
image.plot(zlim=range(Corr, na.rm=T), legend.only=TRUE,
horizontal=T, smallplot=place, xlab="", ylab="", col=Col)
contour(Corr, nlevels = 5, add=T) # Select 5 clusters.

##### Simpson's paradox #####

CF <- 3 # 3rd confounder.
NL <- 10 # Number of levels for confounder.
x11()
z <- dat[,confn[CF]]
probs <- seq(0.01,0.99, length=NL)
Q <- quantile(z, probs = probs)
CI_inter <- matrix(nrow=NL, ncol=2)
CI_inter[,] <- NA
plot(c(1,1), ylim=range(dat[,outcomen]), xlim=range(dat[,treatn]), cex=0,
xlab="Treatment/Radiation (W/m^2)", ylab="Outcome/Temperature (C)")
for(j in 2:length(probs)){
flag <- z >= Q[j-1] & z < Q[j]
points(dat[flag,treatn], dat[flag,outcomen], cex=0.1, col=j-1)
lm.1 <- lm(dat[flag,outcomen] ~ dat[flag,treatn])
abline(lm.1, col=j-1)
CI_inter[j,] <- confint(lm.1)[2,] # Save CI of slopes for each of NL levels.
}
abline(v=quantile(dat[,treatn], probs=0.5), col=1, lt=2)

x11()
boxplot(t(CI_inter), xlab = "Confounder/Height (gpm)", ylab="Slope CI", axes=F)

```

```

axis(1, labels=round(Q,0), at=c(1:NL), cex.axis=0.8, las=3); axis(2, labels=T); box()
abline(h=0)

#####
CF <- 3 # Which confounder to plot.
x11()
par(mfcol=c(3,2), mar=c(4,4,1,1))
hist(dat[,treatn], breaks=100, xlab="Treatment/Radiation (W/m^2)",
main="", mgp=c(2,1,0))
abline(v=quantile(dat[,treatn], probs=0.5), col=1)
hist(dat[,outcomen], breaks=100, xlab="Outcome/Temperature (C)",
main="", mgp=c(2,1,0))
hist(dat[,confn[CF]], breaks=100, xlab="Confounder/Height (gpm)",
main="", mgp=c(2,1,0))
plot(dat[,treatn], dat[,outcomen], cex=0.5, xlab="Treatment/Radiation (W/m^2)",
ylab="Outcome/Temperature (C)", mgp=c(2,1,0))
plot(dat[,confn[CF]], dat[,treatn], cex=0.5, xlab="Confounder/Height (gpm)",
ylab="Treatment/Radiation (W/m^2)", mgp=c(2,1,0))
plot(dat[,confn[CF]], dat[,outcomen], cex=0.5, xlab="Confounder/Height (gpm)",
ylab="Outcome/Temperature (C)", mgp=c(2,1,0))

##### Dihotomize treatment and Standardize #####

x <- dat[,treatn] # Make binary treatment
thresh <- quantile(x, probs = 0.5, na.rm=T)
treat <- x
treat[x < thresh] <- 0
treat[x >= thresh] <- 1
n0 <- sum(treat==0, na.rm=T)
n1 <- sum(treat==1, na.rm=T)
dat[,treatn] <- treat

temp <- dat # Standardize everything (except treatment).
for(i in 1:418){
  if(i != treatn)
    temp[,i] <- (dat[,i] - mean(dat[,i], na.rm=T)) /sd(dat[,i], na.rm=T)
}
dat <- temp
rm(temp)

##### Compute/store SMD & CIs for each of ntrial samples #####

smd_all <- smd_matched <- matrix(nrow=ntrial, ncol = nconf + 1) # +1 for propensity
smd_before <- numeric(ntrial)
CI_diff <- CI_adj <- CI_match <- matrix(nrow=ntrial, ncol=2)

for(trial in 1:ntrial){
  set.seed(trial)
  print(paste0("Trial ", trial))
  samp <- sample(1:nrow(dat), nn, rep=F)
  Dat <- dat[samp, c(treatn, outcomen, confn)]
  colnames(Dat) <- c("treat", "outcome", paste("z", 1:nconf, sep=""))
  Dat <- data.frame(Dat)

  treat <- Dat[,1]
  outcome <- Dat[,2]
  conf <- Dat[,3:(3+nconf-1)]

  numer <- mean(outcome[treat==1]) - mean(outcome[treat==0])

```

```

denom <- sqrt( var(outcome[treat==1]) + var(outcome[treat==0]))
smd_before[trial] <- numer/denom
CI_diff[trial,] <- t.test( outcome[treat==1], outcome[treat==0])$conf.in

##### Match #####

m.out <- matchit(treat ~ z3 + z24, method="full", distance="glm",
  link="probit", dat=Dat, estimand = "ATE", discard = discard)

cov.names <- names(summary(m.out)$sum.all[,1])          # Identify the 2 confounders
in m.out by their number.
covariates <- as.numeric(substr(cov.names,2,3)[-1])    # covariates in
treatment model.
Ncov <- length(covariates)
smd_all[trial,1:(Ncov +1)] <- summary(m.out)$sum.all[,3] # smd +1 for ps
smd_matched[trial,1:(Ncov +1)] <- summary(m.out)$sum.matched[,3]

m.data <- match.data(m.out, dat=Dat)

outcome.m <- lm(outcome ~ treat * (z3 + z24), data = m.data, weights = weights)
ols.m <-      lm(outcome ~ treat * (z3 + z24), data = Dat[samp,] )

treat <- m.data$treat
wts <- m.data$weights
wts[wts > 100] <- 100          # Place a cap on wts.
m.data$weights <- wts

if(trial == 1){
  x11();
  par(mfrow=c(min(3,Ncov),2), mar=c(4,4,1,1))
  for(i in 2+covariates){# 2 for treatment & outcome, & then covariates.
    z <- m.data[,i]
    z_after_matching_1 <- sample(z[treat==1], 5000*n1/(n0+n1),
      replace=TRUE, prob=wts[treat==1])
    z_after_matching_0 <- sample(z[treat==0], 5000*n0/(n0+n1),
      replace=TRUE, prob=wts[treat==0])
    lim <- range(z, z_after_matching_0, z_after_matching_1)
    qqplot(z[treat==0], z[treat==1], xlim=lim, ylim=lim,
      xlab=paste0("X",i-2,"_control_before"),
      ylab=paste0("X",i-2,"_treated_before"), mgp=c(2,1,0))
    abline(0,1, lt=2)
    qqplot(z_after_matching_0, z_after_matching_1, xlim=lim, ylim=lim,
xlab=paste0("X",i-2,"_control_after"),
      ylab=paste0("X",i-2,"_treated_after"), mgp=c(2,1,0))
    abline(0,1, lt=2)
  }
  # end of for over covariates.

  # Make conditional histogram of ps for each treatment group.
  ps <- m.data$distance # propensity score.
  x11();
  par(mfrow=c(2,1), mar=c(4,4,3,1))
  a <- hist(ps[treat==0], breaks = seq(0,1, length=100), plot=F)
  b <- hist(ps[treat==1], breaks = seq(0,1, length=99), plot=F)
  plot(a$mids, sqrt(a$counts), type="h", xlim=c(0,1), xlab="Propensity Score",
ylab="Frequency", ,mgp=c(2,1,0))
  lines(b$mids+0.00, sqrt(b$counts), type="h", col="red")
  if(discard == "both"){
    PS <- numeric(nrow(Dat)); # Make space for propensity score.
    PS[] <- NA # show discarded points as NA.
  }
}

```

```

        PS[-which(m.out$discarded, arr.ind=T)] <- ps
      }else{
        PS <- ps
      }
    X <- numeric( (xf-x0+1)*(yf-y0+1)) ; X[] <- NA
    X[samp] <- PS
    Y <- matrix(X, ncol=yf-y0+1, byrow=F)
    image(my.transf(Y), col=Col, axes=F) ; box()
    image.plot(zlim=range(Y, na.rm=T), legend.only=TRUE, horizontal=T,
               smallplot=place, xlab="", ylab="", col=Col)
  }      # end of if over trial to make figs for.

tt <- avg_comparisons(ols.m, variables="treat", newdata = Dat[samp,])
CI_adj[trial,] <- c(tt$conf.low, tt$conf.high)
tt <- avg_comparisons(outcome.m, variables="treat", wts="weights", newdata =
m.data)
CI_match[trial,] <- c(tt$conf.low, tt$conf.high)

  }      # end of loop over trial

##### smd and ATE plots #####

x11()
Xlab = c("PS",paste0("X",covariates))
boxplot(smd_all, range=0, ylim = c(-1, quantile(c(smd_all,smd_matched),
probs=c(0.98), na.rm=T)),
        ylab="Standardized Mean Difference", xlab="Confounder/Height (gpm)",
        xlim=c(0.5,Ncov+1.5), axes=F, boxwex=0.7)
boxplot(smd_matched, range=0, add=T, border=2, boxwex=0.7, axes=F) ; abline(h=0)
axis(1, labels=Xlab, at=c(1:(1+Ncov)), cex.axis=1); axis(2, labels=T); box()

x11()
boxplot(t(CI_diff), boxwex=0.7, ylim=range(CI_diff, CI_adj, CI_match),
xlab="Trials", ylab= "ATE")
boxplot(t(CI_adj), add=T, boxwex=0.6, col=2)
boxplot(t(CI_match), add=T, col=4, boxwex=0.5)
abline(h=0)

```